

DEVELOPING ORAL SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

Abstract. The key talent for people to master in their personal, academic, and professional lives is oral communication. Early on, it is essential to create a solid basis for oral speaking skills, and primary school is the perfect setting for doing so. The learning process may be improved by including interactive techniques into the curriculum, which can also inspire students to develop their communication skills. The different interactive techniques that may be used to help primary school kids improve their oral communication abilities are examined in this article.

Keywords: new approaches, games, Speaking skills, young learners, interactive methods.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers and other educators now frequently highlight the need to assess and update the pedagogies being utilized across the world. Even though more schools are reportedly adopting innovative practices, "schools remain largely seen as very resistant places for innovation" (Peterson, Dumont, Lafuente, & Law, 2018, p. 4). In order to create a pleasant learning environment, it is crucial to emphasize the fact that the so-called "joy of teaching" and "joy of learning" go hand in hand (UNICEF, 2006, p. 23). Due to the fact that "interactive methodologies make learning enjoyable and exciting to students and improve their retention, participation, and performance" (UNICEF, 2006, p. 23), child-centered and learner-friendly educational environments are being given top attention. The effectiveness of teaching young learners correlates with a teacher's ability to use a variety of strategies, among which interactive cognitive strategies can help teachers foster "greater attentiveness, interest and responsiveness" in children while improving their language skills (UNICEF, 2006, p. 23). Because of this, a teacher must take into account the pupils' numerous intelligences, including their personality types, modes of thought, range of attention, and capacity for information perception and processing (Korovina, Pushkina, & Krivoshlykova, 2017, p. 10). Evidently, planning and structuring the educational process differently while working with young learners is necessary. The term "meaningful practice" has been highlighted by experts and is defined as "an activity where language control is still provided but where students are required to make meaningful choices when carrying out

practice" (Richards, 2006, p. 16). According to Buhrow and Garcia (2006), meaningful practice leads to meaningful communication because, for children, "learning is all about exploring their passions and interests" (p. VIII). We consider interactive methods (IMs) to be one of the most useful tools in this regard. It facilitates the creation of a cozy learning atmosphere, lowers psychological obstacles, and results in activities that are exciting for young learners. The instructor encourages students to conduct individual information searches and to engage in conversational situations with readiness and passion within the framework of IMs. Figure 01, the flowchart below, shows the vast majority of interactive techniques used in young learners' instructional process.

Main part methods

Interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity. She has very specific and predictable goals in mind. One of these goals is to create comfortable learning conditions, that is, conditions under which the student feels his success, his intellectual competence, which makes the learning process itself productive. The essence of interactive learning is such an organization of the educational process in which almost all students are involved in the learning process, they have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think (Talosa et al., 2021). The joint activity of students in the process of learning, learning a foreign language, means that everyone makes their own special individual contribution to this process, that there is an exchange of knowledge, ideas, ways of activity (Fan & Khattak, 2009). Moreover, this happens in an atmosphere of goodwill and mutual support, which, in turn, gives an excellent opportunity not only to receive new knowledge, but also develops cognitive activity itself, translates it into higher forms of cooperation and cooperation. Interactive learning simultaneously solves several problems: • develops communication skills and abilities, helps to establish emotional contacts between students, helps to overcome the "language barrier"; • solves the information problem, since it provides students with the necessary information on the topic. Interactive learning partly solves another essential problem. We are talking about relaxation, relieving nervous stress, switching attention, changing forms of activity, etc. (Seufert, 2003). The most common interactive methods used in practical classes in learning a language are work in pairs, work in small groups, cluster, syncwine, mind map, fish skeleton, brainstorming, decision tree, roleplaying (business) game, project method.

1. Storytelling and Role-Play: Storytelling and role-play are highly effective techniques that engage students in active learning while developing their oral speech skills. By encouraging students to tell stories or act out scenarios, teachers can stimulate their imagination, vocabulary, and language fluency. These activities enable students to construct narratives, use expressive language, and practice effective communication with their peers.

2. Debates and Discussions: Debates and discussions provide opportunities for students to articulate their opinions, present arguments, and

engage in critical thinking. Teachers can introduce age-appropriate topics and encourage students to research and prepare their arguments. By participating in debates and discussions, students not only develop their oral speech skills but also learn to respect diverse viewpoints and hone their persuasive abilities.

1) Public Speaking and Presentations: Giving presentations or speeches in front of an audience helps students build confidence, improve articulation, and enhance their communication skills. Teachers can assign topics or allow students to choose their own, ensuring they cover a range of subjects. By incorporating visual aids, such as PowerPoint presentations or posters, students learn to organize their thoughts and present information effectively.

4. Group Projects and Collaborative Learning: Collaborative projects promote teamwork, cooperation, and communication among students. Assigning group tasks where students need to brainstorm ideas, plan, and present their work together fosters oral speech skills. Students learn to listen actively, express their thoughts, and engage in meaningful conversations to accomplish a common goal.

- Digital Tools and Educational Technology: Leveraging digital tools and educational technology can make learning interactive and engaging for primary school students. Online platforms, such as video conferencing, interactive whiteboards, and educational apps, offer opportunities for students to practice their oral speech skills remotely. Virtual presentations, online debates, and interactive quizzes can enhance student engagement and provide immediate feedback.

6. Language Games and Activities: Integrating language games and activities into the curriculum adds an element of fun while enhancing oral speech skills. Activities like tongue twisters, word puzzles, charades, and storytelling games encourage students to practice pronunciation, expand their vocabulary, and improve their fluency. These interactive games create a positive learning environment and motivate students to communicate with enthusiasm.

CONCLUSION:

Developing oral speech skills is essential for primary school students as it lays the foundation for effective communication throughout their lives. Incorporating interactive methods into the curriculum not only enhances their oral speech abilities but also makes learning enjoyable and engaging. By incorporating storytelling, role-play, debates, discussions, group projects, digital tools, and language games, teachers can create a dynamic learning environment that nurtures confident and effective communicators. Emphasizing interactive methods in primary education empowers students with the essential skills needed to express their thoughts, engage with others, and succeed in various aspects of life.

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